

Use of Health Services Research for Quality Improvements in Primary Healthcare Services in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Health systems research can be an important tool supporting quality improvement in health care services. There are various examples of research supporting quality improvement on the international level. This project presents the local-level efforts to use health services research as a tool to support quality improvement in health care services. The challenge has always been formulating good research questions that identify needed actions and interventions to improve healthcare services and patient outcomes. This project explains how health research supports quality improvement in healthcare provision and improves patients' local outcomes.

Methods: The study primarily focused on health services research over the past few years that was conducted at the Family and Community Medicine Dept, which was planned for health services quality improvement and to support decision-making and improving quality of services provided that ultimately led to improved patient outcomes and reduced morbidity and related costs.

Results: in this study, our project yielded a noteworthy result of solid examples of research supporting improved quality of health care provided and decision making. Research on needs assessment for different types of clinics, research on patient population health needs assessment, and impact of interventions and their utility for general use in all primary health care settings.

Conclusion: The project centered around health research activities within primary healthcare settings. By specifically explaining how it supports improvement in healthcare quality and improved patient outcomes, there is a promising opportunity to enhance healthcare quality provided to patients through the ongoing research aiming to improvement of quality in primary healthcare. The results underscore the significance of integrating research activities and continuous quality improvement in health care provision which ultimately leads to reduced morbidity and mortality and improved patient outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Introduction

Problem Description

The goal of all healthcare professionals is to improve patients' outcomes. A variety of interventions can improve the quality of healthcare provided. These interventions usually rely on evidence-based utility and impact on favorable outcomes and patient outcomes. The problem is that evidence derived from

international research is not usually suited to our local healthcare needs and setting. The challenge was to design and conduct well-planned research studies to answer pressing questions for improving patient outcomes and improving healthcare quality in the national kingdom healthcare services and local level in the Family and Community Medicine Department at Prince Sultan Military Medical City.

More Information

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Available Knowledge

Definition of research: It is defined as a systematic investigation to advance existing knowledge, by answering a research question.

Why to do research? To summarize it's to Understand the causes of a problem, improve programs/services, market programs/services, assess needs, access Resources, to be able to offer new programs/services, develop partnerships, and contribute to scientific knowledge. And simply from these items, we can see it integral part for health services quality improvement. So, health services research can be used as a tool to improve the quality of health services, reflected in Reduced morbidity, Improved prognosis, and Reduced mortality.

Research is critical in healthcare quality improvement (QI), as it provides evidence-based insights that guide effective interventions and strategies. Here's a detailed look at the different roles of research in healthcare QI, Research can support healthcare quality improvements through the following:

1. Identifying Problems and Needs: Research helps to identify gaps in healthcare delivery and areas where patient outcomes can be improved. Through systematic data collection and analysis, research provides a clear picture of the current state of healthcare services. An example of that was A study conducted by Pronovost et al. (2006) [1] demonstrated the need for improved infection control practices, leading to the development of a checklist for central line insertion that significantly reduced bloodstream infections in intensive care units.
2. Developing and Testing Interventions: once problems are identified, research helps in developing and testing interventions to address these issues. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), cohort studies, and other research methodologies are used to evaluate the effectiveness of different interventions. An Example of that is The Institute of Healthcare Improvement's (IHI) Model for Improvement uses Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles to test changes on a small scale before wider implementation [2].
3. Measuring Outcomes and Impact: also, research provides tools and methodologies to measure the impact of QI interventions. This includes both process measures (e.g., adherence to clinical guidelines) and outcome measures (e.g., reduction in patient mortality rates). An example of that is the study published in the Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA) showed that implementing a surgical safety checklist reduced postoperative complications and deaths, demonstrating the checklist's effectiveness in improving surgical outcomes [3].
4. Guiding Policy and Practice: research findings inform healthcare policies and clinical practice guidelines. By providing evidence of what works and what doesn't, research helps in setting standards for quality care. An

example of that is the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in the UK uses systematic reviews and meta-analyses to develop evidence-based guidelines that healthcare providers are encouraged to follow [4].

5. Facilitating Continuous Learning and Improvement: in a way that research contributes to a culture of continuous learning and improvement by identifying best practices and encouraging healthcare providers to engage in ongoing education and training. An example of that is the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), which funds and disseminates research to help healthcare organizations implement and sustain quality improvement initiatives, promoting a learning health system [5].

6. Enhancing Patient-Centered Care: research in patient preferences, experiences, and outcomes ensures that quality improvement initiatives are aligned with patient needs and expectations. This enhances the overall quality of care and patient satisfaction. An example for that is studies on patient-centered care models, such as shared decision-making, which have shown that involving patients in their care plans leads to better health outcomes and higher satisfaction rates [6].

7. Ensuring Safety and Reducing Errors: research identifies potential safety risks and develops strategies to mitigate these risks, thus reducing the likelihood of medical errors and adverse events. An example of that is the development of barcoding systems for medication administration, supported by research evidence, which has significantly reduced medication errors in hospitals [7].

8. Supporting Cost-Effectiveness: research helps to identify cost-effective interventions that can improve care quality without increasing healthcare costs. This is crucial for sustainable healthcare delivery. An Example for that are economic evaluations of healthcare interventions, such as the cost-effectiveness of different cancer screening programs, which guide resource allocation decisions [8].

Rationale

Research is a cornerstone of quality improvement of healthcare services, providing the evidence base for effective decision-making and practice. Health services research not only helps identify areas for improvement but also tests and validates interventions, measures outcomes, and informs policies. By doing so, research ensures that healthcare systems are continuously evolving and improving to meet the needs of patients and providers alike.

Why research? The answer to this question is to provide better care for our patients. Through research, we want to improve the quality of primary care services by improving our understanding and practice of it [9].

The Model for Health Research Integrated into Health Services Quality Improvement. Example: Patients'

knowledge about long-term risks of Diabetes Mellitus:
Is it beneficial to explain long-term risks of DM by family
medicine physicians to DM Patients?

Table 1: A Model for Integrating Research into Quality Improvement Components

Foci	Dimensions		
	Structure	Process	Outcome
Basic knowledge			
Problem-solving approach			
Practice Implementation			
Education			

Table 2: Examples for using the Model of applying research topics to the Quality Improvement Model

Foci	Dimensions				
	Structure	Process	Outcome	Research Focus	Research Strategy
Basic knowledge	What do patients know about long-term risks of type 2 diabetes mellitus?	How do family physicians inform their patients about the long-term risks?	With which instruments can we measure the effect of extra information on the patient's compliance with therapy and follow-up?	Concepts	Exploratory descriptive, both quantitative and qualitative
Problem-solving approach	Can looking at an educational videotape improve this knowledge in a small group of voluntary patients?	Will the development of a practice guideline with special attention to informing patients about their disease make doctors (an experimental group of volunteers) give more information to their patients?	Are better informed patients more compliant (tested in an experimental group of volunteers)?	Efficacy	Experimental-controlled
Implementation	Will distributing these videotapes to all patients improve their knowledge of diabetes?	Will the introduction of their guidance on a large scale (sent by mail to all family giving information to diabetics in general)?	Does the general increase in patients' knowledge about their illness lead to a general increase in compliance?	Effectiveness	Experimental
Policy	What is the cost of this intervention in relation in to the benefits?	What is the cost of developing and distributing this guideline in relation to the benefits?	Is the cost to achieve this increase in compliance in balance with the possible benefits, and does this contribute to more equity?	Efficiency	Health economics
Education	What should be the content of a course on focused on the context socially vulnerable groups?	Is role-playing an effective way to teach students to give clear information to diabetic patients on their disease?	Do students effectively learn to evaluate the patient's compliance during their internships?	Education (knowledge, skills, attitudes)	Variable

The matrix (Table 1) above simplifies the focus and contents of the health research for service quality improvement; the focus can range from basic knowledge, problem-solving approach, practice implementation, policy contents, and or education methods; all these contents are in a matrix with the

standard three components of health services quality program contents of structure, process, and outcomes. To elaborate more on such a model, we will use the applied research question that needed to be answered, is it beneficial to explain the long-term risks of DM by family medicine physicians to DM patients?

Then we will have the following model that can cross the gap between health research and quality improvement in health care [9].

Examples (Table 2) of using such a model in crossing the gap between health research and health services quality improvement:

1. Structure of basic knowledge: what do diabetes mellitus patients already know about the long-term risks of DM?
2. Process and problem-solving approach: will the development of a practice guideline with special attention to informing patients about their disease make doctors give more information to patients?
3. Testing implementation outcomes: does a general increase in the patient's knowledge about their illness lead to a general rise in compliance?

So, these matrix and example research questions integrated with the three service quality components can illustrate the approach all of us as healthcare professionals should adopt for better patient healthcare outcomes.

Specific Aims

1. To identify research conducted at FCM Dept aiming to support quality improvement;
2. To identify how research can support quality improvement in healthcare;
3. To identify models for integrating research and quality improvement in health care services.

Context

Clinical research is vital to continually improve the clinical effectiveness of medicine and primary health care. Most clinical practice guidelines adopted nowadays were developed with the support of clinical research. Research is defined as a systematic investigation to advance existing knowledge by answering a research question. Good research starts with good questions, these research questions mostly range around what we should do for better patient health care and better patient outcomes. Quality improvement is defined as the systematic and continual actions that result in measurable improvement in local settings. A key outcome of quality improvement is providing the best care to the right patients by designing, assessing, and altering the healthcare system.

There has been use of health research for health services quality improvement at the international level for decades:

1. There was a debate in the 1970th on whether to use 100% O₂ for neonates to increase survival compared to less O₂ concentration, unfortunately, some cases of blindness were reported. And there was a question: Does 100% O₂ inhalation for newborns pose a risk for later blindness (Retrolental fibrosis)? In this research, Lanman and colleagues proved that the use of 100% O₂ for premature newborns leads to

retrolental fibrosis and later blindness, compared to no blinding among newborns administered regular concentration O₂. This is considered landmark research that improved the quality of health care services provided by reduction and prevention of blinding and morbidity due to the use of 100% O₂ among newborns [10].

2. Research has documented that lack of access to health care results in poorer health outcomes. (Mick et al., 1994). This landmark study led to the focus on importance of accessibility and equity in health care coverage and provision since lack of access and health care provision leads to population morbidity and mortality in higher rates [11].

3. Research has demonstrated that preventive services (e.g., mammography) substantially reduce mortality and morbidity at reasonable costs. (Mandelblatt et al., 2003). The cost-effectiveness of screening mammography beyond age 65 years: a systematic review for the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. This landmark study led to the universal recommendations for the preventive periodic mammography for women [12].

4. There was a question on whether nursing staffing and its shortage affect the patient health outcomes and quality of services provided. The research work by Needleman and his colleagues has established a causal link between nursing shortage and Poor patient health outcomes (Needleman et al., 2002). this study led to the acknowledgment that nursing understaffing in healthcare settings leads to unwanted higher rates of morbidity and mortality among patients [13].

5. There was a universal observation that some cases of breast cancer develop relapses compared to others. So, the raised research question was what are the differences between breast cancer cases with relapses compared to those without relapse? The answer was achieved using research methods of breast cancer cases case-control study design which identified the difference of HER2 receptor is higher among cases of cancer breast relapse compared to those without relapse. So, the development of vital life savings guidelines of care for breast cancer cases for testing of HER2 receptor and treatment with Herceptin to those who are HER2 receptor-positive cases. So, improvement of quality of health care services provided to breast cancer patients through the use of Herceptin to improve the prognosis of breast cancer. This study improved the outcomes for many breast cancer patients who are HER 2 positive by using the treatment of Herceptin [14].

6. Studies in the 1970s found that folate deficiency was associated with higher rates of Neural Tube Defects (NTDs), and in the 1980s found that use of folate supplements was associated with decreased

rates of NTDs. Also, research findings led to the recommendations for the use of folic acid to reduce the number of cases of spina bifida and other neural tube defects. This study led to the universal recommendation for the use of folate supplementation during pregnancy to prevent neural tube defects and Spina Bifida diseases [15].

So, to summarize why and what to research for quality improvement quality in health care?

Research can help improve the quality of healthcare services in many ways, including:

- Identifying best practices: Research can help determine the best treatments and practices for different conditions by studying factors like diet, lifestyle, and family support. It can also help develop guidelines for best practices.
- Understanding patient perspectives: research can provide firsthand documentation of patient experiences, which can help identify concerns and desires about the quality of care.
- Keeping medical professionals up to date: research helps medical professionals stay current with the latest advancements and techniques in their fields.
- Improving patient outcomes: research can help determine which interventions and treatments are most effective for specific patient populations or conditions. This knowledge can help nurses provide high-quality care and improve patient outcomes.

- Standardizing care: research utilization can help ensure that care is standardized and effective. Research can help improve health service quality by answering pressing questions that arise during healthcare provisions,

Interventions

The Family Medicine Department at Prince Sultan Military Medical City is a major healthcare services provider, both therapeutic and preventive health services. The use of health services research has been an integral part of improving the quality of services provided for patients and reducing morbidity and mortality.

There are many Interventions to illustrate such integration of health research and health services quality improvement, the following are examples of such interventions:

Intervention #1:

Research question: Is there a need to establish a virtual clinic in PHCs to improve Health care service Quality?

This research question was raised even before the COVID-19 era, and there was a pressing need to answer the question to answer that question researchers need to address challenges facing virtual clinic startups as follows in Figure 1, and to explain the process map for establishing a successful virtual clinic in PHCs, in Figure 2. In a research paper published [16]:

Results:

Figure 1: Fishbone Analysis for Challenges of Virtual Clinic in PHC

Figure 2. Diagram for Process Map of Flow of Work with Virtual Patients and Showing Entry and Exit of Patients

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: Virtual clinics were justified and recommended to be generalized to PHCs.

Intervention #2:

Research Question: Is there a need to improve Latent TB screening among new hires at PSMMC?

This question was raised because the majority of new hires at PSMMC were from the Middle East and Southeast Asia, where there are higher rates of TB in these countries.

The questions were answered by the research work of Mostafa Kofi and colleagues, in the research publication [17].

Results

This work proved from the study that there are high rates of positive PPD according to nationality Table 3, so, the study findings necessitate PPD screening and adding even a two-step PPD, to improve the quality of Latent TB screening.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Positive PPD According to Nationality among all HCWs Tested

			PPD		Total
			Negative	Positive	
Nationality	Middle East	Count	3126	109	3235
		% within Nationality	96.6%	3.4%	100.0%
	East Asia	Count	2793	187	2980
		% within Nationality	93.7%	6.3%	100.0%
	Africa	Count	101	14	115
		% within Nationality	87.8%	12.2%	100.0%
	Western Pacific	Count	70	4	74
		% within Nationality	94.6%	5.4%	100.0%
Total		Count	6090	314	6404
		% within Nationality	95.1%	4.9%	100.0%

Table 6 in the research published by the researchers that the bulk of positive PPD new hires come from the Middle East and Southeast Asia.

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: improved process for PPD testing and adding a second step PPD to minimize false negatives.

Intervention #3:

Research Question: Is there a beneficial impact of Home Health care in reducing readmission rates?

The questions were answered by the research work of research Dr. Medhat Maher and colleagues [18].

This work proved the reduced rates of hospital readmission among patients in home health care of the FCM Dept., compared to those who are not in the home health care program and discharged to private homes, also proved cost reductions associated with these readmission rates reduction from table 4.

Results:

Table 4: Readmission Rate ang patient discharge to Their to Their Houses and Those Discharged to HHC

Group	Number	Read within 30 days N (%)	95% Confidence interval
Patient discharged to HHC	818	117 (14.3%)	[0.429, 0.608]
Patient discharged to their houses	4904	1373 (28%)	
P value		0.001	

Table 1 findings revealed that the statistics of PSMMC patients with the major three chronic diseases (DM, HTN & Dementia) in 2018 revealed that the total number of patients discharged from PSMMC was 5722. Out of these patients, 818 patients were discharged to Home Health Care (HHC) and 4904 patients were discharged to their houses. Among those discharged to HHC, 117 were readmitted to PSMMC (14.3%), while 1373 of those discharged to their houses were readmitted (28%). The effect of the home healthcare services had a 50% reduction of readmission for the three major diseases under study compared to the standard patient, with a relative risk of 0.5 (95%CI 0.429-0.608).

Analysis and Impact of research on service Quality: there is a 50 % reduction in the probability of being readmitted to the hospital within one month of discharge if discharged to the Home Health Care program of FCM Dept. at PSMMC.

Intervention #4:

Research Question: To what extent the hand hygiene among health care workers?

The questions were answered by the research work of Sultan Almutairi and colleagues, in which he surveyed

all nursing staff and physicians on when should have hand hygiene and how to do I [19].

This cross-sectional study included clinical staff working at PHC centers. A pre-validate questionnaire was used with an observational approach of applying HH among the study sample. The data were analyzed using SPSS software, and descriptive statistics and logistic regression models were produced.

Results:

Of 425 clinical study participants, 263 (61.9%) were females, 169 (39.8%) were in the age group 31-39 years, 215 (50.6%) were nurses/laboratory specialists, and 281 (33.9%) were from departments of high risk of contamination. Overall, the average knowledge score was 75%. However, there were significantly higher scores in knowledge level among nurses and laboratory specialists than the rest (P<0.01) and three times likely the more positive practice of hand hygiene in comparison to others [Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR) = 3.285, 95% CI, 1.764-6.116].

This work proved that the average knowledge score is 75% and practice of hand hygiene is more positive among nursing staff.

Figure 3: Hand Hygiene Training Rates and Used of alcohol-based Hand Rub (Last 3 Years)

In Figure 3 of this study, the left side of the figure shows the percentage of the health care workers who received training (yes) in the past on hand hygiene and those who had not received it (no). The other side (right) of the figure, showed those healthcare workers routinely using alcohol-based hand rubs (yes) and those not used (no). also, the majority of the health care workers (75.8%) had received formal training in hand hygiene in the last 3 years (yes). On the other side, almost all the (94.8%) healthcare workers routinely used an alcohol-based hand rub (yes).

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: Development of educational programs for improving and encouraging hand hygiene among healthcare workers.

Intervention #5:

Research Question: Is there a need for psychotherapy training for HCWs in PHCs?

The questions were answered by the research work of Dr. Lara Alnamlah and colleagues [20].

This work proved that primary care physicians need more training and orientation on psychotherapy. The average knowledge score for psychotherapy was

90.7%. There is no evidence, using regression analysis, of an association between knowledge score and the physician’s characteristics. The answers in the attitude section revealed a positive attitude from the family physicians towards psychotherapy, along with a willingness to be trained. Majority of PHC physicians indicated they are already practicing psychotherapy at their clinics. There are several prominent barriers to conducting psychotherapy within PHC clinical settings e.g. lack of time, lack of training, and lack of skills.

Results:

This study shows a prominent level of knowledge regarding psychotherapy, a positive attitude towards it, and an agreed-upon need and willingness to attend psychotherapy training among PHC physicians. Additionally, most of the physicians reported practicing psychotherapy at their clinics. However, there are several barriers that need to be tackled to improve the practice.

Figure 4 in the study reveals that PHC physicians are variably refer patients to psychotherapy clinics in the hospital.

Figure 4: Frequency of Referring Patients for Psychotherapy when Indicated

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: Establishment of an adult psychology clinic at PHC and establishment of its roles and responsibility of psychotherapy and counseling.

Intervention #6:

Research Question: Are nursing staff immune against vaccine-preventable diseases in new hires at PSMHC?

The questions were answered by the research work of Dr. Mostafa Kofi and colleagues [21].

In this work screening for immunity among nursing staff found that 79.3% were immune against measles; 75.5% were immune against mumps; 95.8% were immune against rubella; and 67% were immune against varicella. The highest proportion of immune nursing staff against measles (96.3%) and varicella

(93.5%) was found in the intensive care department while the highest proportion of immune staff against mumps (89.4%) was found in long stay department, and against rubella (97.5%) in hemodialysis department. On the other hand, it was found that hemodialysis department had the highest proportion of non-immune staff against measles (35.6%), mumps (39%), and varicella (56.3%), while emergency department had the lowest proportion of immune staff (6%) against rubella. So, despite that immunity among nurses screened was good in some departments; however, such results need improvement in these critical areas. These findings emphasize the importance of the currently mandatory screening for MMRV before employment.

Results:

Figures 5 to 8 show immunity and need to be vaccinated among nursing staff newly hired.

Figure 5: Immunity against Measles among Nursing Staff Screened

Figure 6: Immunity against Mumps among Nursing Staff Screened

Figure 7: Immunity against Rubella among Nursing Staff Screened

Figure 8: Immunity against Varicella among Nursing Staff Screened

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: awareness campaign during orientation of the new hires, mandatory testing for immunity against MMRV, and annual examination for immunity among nursing staff.

Intervention #7:

Research Question: What are the challenges of handling patients of COVID-19 when attending the PHC, and how to manage proactively to prevent infection from spreading?

The questions were answered by the research work of Dr. Medhat Maher and colleagues [22].

In this work, researchers face the challenge of dealing with the surge of the COVID-19 pandemic patients in health care facilities need proper ways to effectively detect the patients with flu symptoms and prevent the transmission of the infection to the other patients and the health care workers in the same time. The fundamental aim of this project was to improve early detection and management of COVID-19 patients during covid19 pandemic.

Results:

Researchers used the model of Failure Mode Effect Analysis, (FMEA) as a methodology for improvement starting with the possible risk of transmission of infection during patient movement in Al-Wezzarat primary healthcare center implemented change concepts in the form of

- (1). Reduce unnecessary steps in patients suspected to have COVID-19.
- (2). Performing tasks parallel with the main process,
- (3) Smooth workflow in a step.
- (4). Eliminate hand-off failure.
- (5). Replace with better value steps, based on the outcome redesign the work process.

These led to decreased average pre-consultation from 22 minutes to 1 minute, increased average consultation from 17 to 4 minutes, before swabbing time improved from 7 to 2 minutes, an Improved Pharmacy waiting time from 4 to 1, and patient

journey improved from 50 to 8 minutes. Outcome results: outbreak infection rate among healthcare professionals improved overall from 9.8% to 0.5%. Balancing results overall staff satisfaction improved from 24% to 85%. This work was a role model in situations of uncertainties like covid19 pandemic, urgent management of situations and interventions are needed; and a proactive quality improvement tool like failure mode and effect analysis and change management concept is recommended to improve. Figure 9 shows patient movement in the center before intervention and areas where possible infection transmission to other patients. Figure 10 shows the modifications implemented to proactively control and prevent infection transmission from patients of COVID-19 to other patients attending the PHC.

Figure 9: Possible Risk of Transmission of Infection during Patient Movement in Wazarat Healthcare Center

Figure 10: Redesign of the Patients Flow from the Entrance to Discharge

Figure 10 (a,b): Illustration of the Reduction of Patient Waiting Time and the Interval between Consultations and Medical Manipulations

Figure 10 show decreased waiting times for patients and reduced consultation times for patients.

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: decreased waiting times of patients before consultation and before pharmacy, and decreased consultation times and separate flow of suspected COVID-19 patients led to decreased COVID-19 transmission.

Intervention #8:

Research Question: There was a sharp decline in pediatric vaccination coverage rates during the COVID-19 epidemic, so, how to overcome such a decline in pediatric vaccination coverage rates?

The questions were answered by the research work of Dr. Medhat Maher and colleagues during which he reviewed multiple interventions and tested and reported the beneficial effects of using vaccination teams' mobile units, and proved by research done that pediatric vaccination coverage rates catch up to before COVID-19 pandemic [23].

This work summarizes that pediatric vaccination is a mandatory program to control vaccine-preventable diseases and in such cases that hinder its activity; in which conditions there is increased morbidity and mortality due to these vaccine-preventable diseases. Routine vaccination of children must remain a priority even during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Results:

Figure 11: Improving Pediatric Vaccination during Covid 19 Pandemic 2020

Figure 12: Shows the Head Nurse and the Nurse-coordinator while Inspecting and Checking the Team in the Morning before Heading to the Home Visits to Ensure the Availability of the Required Medical Equipment, Supplies and Vaccines for Patient

Analysis and Impact of Research on Quality of Service:

So, this work proved that System changes to Developing new booking software in the hospital website based on patient geographical distribution, age of the child, and vaccination required to improve the patient access to care to log in and register their child. Integrated this program with healthcare team providers to facilitate the child's home vaccination during the COVID-19 pandemic and to allocate resources with continuity of care considering a safe procedure of vaccination at the patient's house.

Intervention #9:

Research Question: How to reduce rates of pressure ulcers at home health care settings and the associated cost reduction?

The questions were answered by the research work of Dr. Abdulaziz Bin Rasheed and colleagues [24].

The goal of this project was to evaluate the effectiveness of risk assessment and preventive management plans for pressure ulcer prevention among patients admitted to HHC, PSMMC. The researchers used the Braden Scale to assess patient risk for possible development of pressure ulcers, and from this, a preventive action plan was adopted from Nice Guideline 2018 according to the patient level of risk.

Results:

So, the research showed that over the 6-month duration of the study in which we used the Braden Scale, we saw a six percent decrease in the incidence of pressure ulcers. As for the duration of care, this study saw a reduction from 4 months of care per ulcer to only 1.67 months of care per ulcer.

Table 5: Time Saved by Implementing the Braden Scale

	Before Implementing the Braden Scale	After Implementing the Braden Scale
Total number of ulcers in 2017 is	1 358x5 000\$	1 276x5 000\$
6% reduction		82x5 000\$=410 000\$
Time to care	1 358x4 Month Care	1 276x1.67 Month Care
Direct costs of ulcer care	1 354x4=5 432x2 000\$=27 160 000\$	1 276x1.67=2 131x2 000\$=4 264 000\$
Estimate costs reduction	27 160 000-4 264 000=22 896 000\$	

Table 5 shows the reduction in the number of bed ulcers and associated costs before and after the implementation of the Braden scale for ulcer care

among home healthcare patients at the Family and Community Medicine Department at PSMMC.

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: the researchers estimated that PSMMC would save more than \$22 million annually using these measures. Also, the incidence rate of pressure ulcer development improved compared to patients without the implementation of the program. Overall burdens, including time and financial costs, are reduced. The researchers recommended that such a program emphasizes proactive risk assessment, management plan, staff development, and patient care education to help in the active prevention of pressure ulcers.

Intervention #10:

Research Question: What is the impact and what are the challenges for the newly established Psychotherapy clinic in PHCs?

The research work by Nouf Aljunaidel and colleagues answered the questions [25]:

There is a need to raise awareness of the importance of integration of psychotherapy into primary care settings because it may increase access to mental health treatment and improve patient outcomes. So, the researchers conducted A retrospective case study was conducted using clinic performance reports and patient appointment data in 2023 and the Q1 of year 2024. Such data included appointment bookings, demographics of patients, discharge rates, and no-show rates. The findings of the research suggest that integrating psychotherapy improves service availability showed by lower wait times and more people being discharged, which could indicate successful therapy. However, challenges still exist such as high no-show rates that might result from appointment scheduling challenges or social determinants affecting health and a more holistic approach to dealing with psychological influences on mental health should be adopted.

Results:

Figure 13 show increased rates and upward pattern for use of psycho-therapy clinic services in PHC during the 2023 by months.

Figure 13: Mental Health Psychology 2023

Analysis and Impact of Research on Service Quality: The consolidation of psychotherapy services in primary healthcare is optimistic for mental healthcare accessibility and patient well-being. Nonetheless, addressing issues like no-shows and social determinants of illnesses is vital if the program is to be further optimized. Program effectiveness and patient care are improved through continued cooperation with primary care clinics and social services. as well as better data collection.

Study of the interventions

Each intervention was evaluated against a set of criteria, whether it answered the raised question, and whether the intervention ultimately led to the introduction of a new service, the development or improvement of current services, or explained and confirmed the need for health services modifications.

Measures

In each intervention, the standard research methodology was used aiming to identify what to be addressed to improve the quality of services for patients. Quantitative methods for differences in mean and proportions were commonly used, to compare before and after implementation of test measures, or the impact of starting new clinic services, or even to monitor the use and success of a newly established and running new service.

Analysis

- In intervention #1: A study of the process and challenges facing the establishment of a virtual clinic in the PHCs at PSMMC, concluded with the identification of such challenges and measures to overcome and the pressing needs for starting such services in PHCs at PSMMC.
- In intervention #2: Descriptive statistics for the surveillance data of pre-employment screening covering screening for Latent TB.
- In intervention #3: A comparative study of the differences in proportions for the readmission of patients to PSMMC hospital after discharge between those who are at the Home Health Care program of the Family and Community Medicine Department at PSMMC, and the private home care.
- In intervention #4: A general survey was used to address the knowledge and practices of HCWs at PHC of hand hygiene, and conclusions were made on the proportions of HCWs with enough knowledge and correct practices of hand hygiene.
- In intervention #5: Same as in intervention #4, A general survey questionnaire was used to address psychotherapy training needs assessment for PHC physicians, and according to the proportions of the findings, a conclusion agreed on the need for such training.

- In Intervention #6: Same as in Intervention #2; Descriptive statistics for the surveillance data of pre-employment screening for immunity against vaccine-preventable disease were studied in this research, and conclusions were drawn on which geographical areas with a higher proportion of non-immune HCWs. Accordingly, emphasis was drawn on the orientation and implementation of mandatory vaccination programs for new hires.

- In intervention #7: Researchers used the model of Failure Mode Effect Analysis, (FMEA) as a Methodology for improvement starting with the Possible risk of transmission of infection during patient movement in Al-Wezzarat Primary Healthcare Center implemented change concepts in the form of

- (1). Reduce unnecessary steps in patients suspected to have COVID-19.
- (2). Performing tasks parallel with the main process,
- (3) Smooth workflow in a step.
- (4) Eliminate hand-off failure.
- (5) Replace with better value steps, based on the outcome redesign the work process.

These led to decreased average Pre-consultation from 22 minutes to 1 minute, increased average consultation from 17 to 4 minutes, before swabbing time improved from 7 to 2 minutes, an Improved Pharmacy waiting time from 4 to 1, and Patient journey improved from 50 to 8 minutes.

- In intervention #8: researchers used the approach of testing system changes and its impact on rates of pediatric vaccination, and it proved undoubtedly that these changes implemented including the development of an online booking system for pediatric vaccination and mobile teams for vaccination was successful in getting back pediatric vaccination rates to its pre-COVID-19 era rates.

- In intervention #9 researchers calculated the cost reduction due to the reduction in bed ulcer cases and extrapolated the cost reduction possible if the Braden scale is applied for all cases of bed ulcer reported.

- in intervention# 10, researchers used the trend of using the psychotherapy clinic services over a time in a duration of 12 months, during which there was evidence of the increased interest of patients to access the psychotherapy clinic services.

Results

The current project presented ten examples of health services research that supported quality improvement in health care services, these improvements led to improved quality of patient care, reduced morbidity and mortality, addition to reduced costs, the establishment of virtual clinics in PHCs. The reduced numbers of bed ulcers and consequent huge cost savings for bed ulcer cases avoided.

Health services research on how to improve coverage rates of pediatric vaccination led to catch up of vaccination rates for the pre COVID-10 era, this catches up of vaccination rates has a major impact on reduction of morbidity rates and costs related to increased numbers of cases of vaccine-preventable diseases.

Also, research on the best approaches to handling suspected cases of COVID-19 in PHCs to reduce infection transmission led to the reduction of COVID-19 transmission to other patients and to even reduction of COVID-19 infection transmission to health care workers. These were direct and measurable achievements, additionally, indirect reduction in costs for managing prevented new cases of COVID-19 cases either among patients or among HCWs

All ten Healthcare services research interventions that were illustrated a model for collaboration between healthcare services research and quality improvement. All interventions are aimed at improving the quality of care for patients. There is always a need for a multi-disciplinary team for a successful improvement in health care services that are comprised from Quality improvement experts and health care services research specialists, such collaboration will lead to improved patient care and reduced morbidity and mortality.

Discussion

Each intervention is illustrated under section Interventions explain that there has been an impact of each intervention and service provided, and there have been multiple studies on the international level with the same results.

From intervention #1: researchers addressed the challenges and needs assessment to establish virtual clinics in PHCs, and the research work resulted in that virtual clinics were justified and recommended to be generalized to PHCs.

From Intervention #2: the researchers proved the bulk of positive PPD new hires come from the Middle East and Southeast Asia. This led to an improved process for PPD testing and adding a second step PPD to minimize false negatives.

From Intervention #3: to decide whether Home Health Care impacted the readmission of patients after discharge from the hospital PSMMC, this research work proved that the Home Health Care Program by the Family and Community Medicine Department at PSMMC, reduced the number of readmissions and there is a 50 % reduction in the probability of being readmitted to the hospital within one month of discharge if discharged to the Home Health Care program of FCM Dept. at PSMMC.

Intervention #4: identified the need for hand hygiene and hand training so, consequently, Development of educational programs for improving and encouraging hand hygiene among healthcare workers.

From intervention #5: the research work identified the need for an adult psycho-therapy clinic in PHC, consequently, led to the establishment of an adult psychology clinic at PHC and the establishment of its roles and responsibilities of psychotherapy and counseling.

From intervention #6: this research work aimed to identify the needs for raising immunity against vaccine-preventable infectious diseases. So, a developed awareness campaign during orientation of the new hires, mandatory testing for immunity against MMRV, and annual examination for immunity among nursing staff.

From intervention #7: this research work led to the outcome of there has been decreased waiting times of patients before consultation and before pharmacy, and decreased consultation times and separate flow of suspected COVID-19 patients led to decreased COVID-19 transmission.

From intervention #8: This work proved that System changes to Developing new booking software in the hospital website based on patient geographical distribution, age of the child, and vaccination required to improve the patient access to care to log in and register their child. Integrated this program with healthcare team providers to facilitate the child's home vaccination during the COVID-19 pandemic and to allocate resources with continuity of care considering a safe procedure of vaccination at the patient's house.

From intervention #9: the research showed that a reduction in the number of bed ulcers and associated costs before and after the implementation of the Braden scale for ulcer care among home healthcare patients at the Family and Community Medicine Department at PSMCC. So, the researchers estimated that PSMCC would save more than \$22 million annually using these measures. Also, the incidence rate of pressure ulcer development improved compared to patients without implementation of the program. Overall burdens, including time and financial costs, are reduced. The researchers recommended that such a program emphasizes proactive risk assessment, management plan, staff development, and patient care education to help in the active prevention of pressure ulcers.

From intervention #10, showed that there is increasing trend for patients to use the psychotherapy clinic services, consequently confirming the need to consolidation of psychotherapy services in primary healthcare is optimistic for mental healthcare accessibility and patient well-being. Nonetheless, addressing issues like no-shows and social determinants of illnesses is vital if the program is to be further optimized. Program effectiveness and patient care are improved through continued

cooperation with primary care clinics and social services. as well as better data collection.

Limitations

There are so many examples of such collaboration of research to support quality improvement in health services, but unfortunately, limited time and resources to explain more areas of overlapping similar objectives for improvements and mutual interest for improved patient care. Collaboration of quality improvement experts and health services research experts will enhance such work in the future.

Conclusions

Although both quality improvement and health services research aim to enhance patient care, there are distinct variations in their objectives, duration, project structure, scope of intervention, adaptability to environmental changes, approaches to assessing validity, and sources of funding. Quality improvement activities often employ the Plan-Do-Study-Act methodology and other rapid assessment cycles to address medical errors and/or improve the efficiency of care. Health services research is an interdisciplinary field that aims to determine the most efficient ways to organize, provide, and finance healthcare to optimize the quality and value of care at both the individual and population levels. Collaboration between experts in quality improvement and health services research can harness the strengths of each discipline to enhance the quality of delivery of care.

References

- [1] Pronovost P, Needham D, Berenholtz S, et al. An intervention to decrease catheter-related bloodstream infections in the ICU. *N Engl J Med*. 2006;355(26):2725-2732. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa061115
- [2] Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI). How to improve. <http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/default.aspx>
- [3] Haynes AB, Weiser TG, Berry WR, et al. A surgical safety checklist to reduce morbidity and mortality in a global population. *N Engl J Med*. 2009;360(5):491-499. doi:10.1056/NEJMs0810119
- [4] National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). Developing NICE guidelines: The manual. <https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg20/chapter/introduction>
- [5] Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ). About AHRQ. <https://www.ahrq.gov/>
- [6] Barry MJ, Edgman-Levitan S. Shared decision-making—the pinnacle of patient-centered care. *N Engl J Med*. 2012;366(9):780-781. doi:10.1056/NEJMp1109283
- [7] Poon EG, Keohane CA, Yoon CS, et al. Effect of bar-code technology on the safety of medication

administration. *N Engl J Med.* 2010;362(18):1698-1707. doi:10.1056/NEJMsa0907115

[8] Neumann PJ, Sandberg EA, Bell CM, Stone PW, Chapman RH. Are pharmaceuticals cost-effective? A review of the evidence. *Health Aff (Millwood).* 2005;24(5):104-122. doi:10.1377/hlthaff.24.5.104

[9] De Maeseneer JM, De Sutter A. Why research in family medicine? A superfluous question. *Ann Fam Med.* 2004;2 Suppl 2. doi:10.1370/afm.148

[10] Lanman JT, Guy LP, Dancis J. Retrolental fibroplasia and oxygen therapy. *JAMA.* 1954;155(3):223-226. doi:10.1001/jama.1954.03690210001001

[11] Mick SS, Morlock LL, Salkever D, et al. Strategic activity and financial performance of U.S. rural hospitals: A national study, 1983 to 1988. *J Rural Health.* 1994;10(1):29-48. doi:10.1111/j.1748-0361.1994.tb00225.x

[12] Mandelblatt J, Saha S, Teutsch S, et al. The cost-effectiveness of screening mammography beyond age 65 years: A systematic review for the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. *Ann Intern Med.* 2003;139(10):835-842. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-139-10-200311180-00011

[13] Needleman J, Buerhaus P, Mattke S, Stewart M, Zelevinsky K. Nurse-staffing levels and the quality of care in hospitals. *N Engl J Med.* 2002;346(22):1715-1722. doi:10.1056/NEJMsa012247

[14] Slamon DJ, Clark GM, Wong SG, Levin WJ, Ullrich A, McGuire WL. Human breast cancer: Correlation of relapse and survival with amplification of the HER-2/neu oncogene. *Science.* 1987;235(4785):177-182. doi:10.1126/science.3798106

[15] Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Recommendations for the use of folic acid to reduce the number of cases of spina bifida and other neural tube defects. *MMWR Recomm Rep.* 1992;41(RR-14):1-7. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1522835/>

[16] Alrabiah A, Ayoub LA, Hashem MA, Kofi M. Needs assessment to implement virtual clinics in primary health care, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Int J Med Health Res.* 2020;6(3):35-42.

[17] Kofi M, Rsheed AB, AlBattal S, AlAbood A, AlOtaibi A, AlQahtani A, et al. Screening for latent TB among HCWs newly hired in a major hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Int J Med Health Res.* 2020;6(3):10-15.

[18] Mohamed MM, Al-Tehewy M, Hakim SA, Bin Rasheed AM, Al Abood A, Kofi MA. Studying the impact of home health care on hospital readmission rate in Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Int J Med Health Res.* 2020;6(3):16-21.

[19] Al Mutairi SM, Alotaibi A, Kofi M, Alsuraimi A, Bawazir A. To what extent the hand hygiene among health care workers. *Int Arch Nurs Health Care.* 2020;6:144. doi:10.23937/2469-5823/1510144

[20] AlNamlah LA, Kofi M. Needs assessment for psychotherapy training among family medicine physicians practicing at PSMCMC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia 2017-2018. *Int J Adv Res Med.* 2020;2(2):75-84. doi:10.22271/27069567.2020.v2.i2a.50

[21] Kofi M, Rsheed AB, AlBattal S, Al Abood A, Alshowair AM, AlQahtani A, et al. Measles, mumps, rubella, and varicella immunity among nursing staff in a major hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2020;9:5339-5344.

[22] Mohamed MM, Al Rasheed A, Alabood A, Alotaibi A, Abdalrouf A, Elsaid T, et al. Proactive improvement for handling patients with COVID-19 during the pandemic in PHC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Acta Sci Med Sci.* 2021;6(1):1-10.

[23] Maher M, Al Rasheed A, Alabood A, Alotaibi A, Elsaid T, Bassim M, et al. Improving pediatric vaccination during COVID-19 pandemic in PHC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Acta Sci Med Sci.* 2021;6(1):1-9.

[24] Rsheed AB, Alabood A, Alsuliman BK, Alhojailan MA, Moharram M, Maher M, et al. Using the Braden Scale and NICE pressure ulcer guidelines to reduce the burden and costs of pressure ulcers. *Acta Sci Med Sci.* 2021;5(12):1-10.

[25] Aljunaidel N, Albattal S, Kofi M. Measuring the impact of and challenges in using psychotherapy sessions in primary health care, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Eur J Med Health Res.* 2024;2(3):98-103.